

IMPORTANCE OF PHARMACOVIGILANCE AND SIGNAL DETECTION IN POST MARKETING SURVEILLANCE FOR DRUG SAFETY

Vivek Upadhyay¹, Abhishek kumar Ojha², Kamal Singh Bani^{3,4}

1. DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACEUTICS, ACCURATE COLLEGE OF PHARMACY, GRETAER NOIDA
2. DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACEUTICS, GOVERNMENT PHARMACY INSTITUTE, BANKA, BIHAR
3. DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACEUTICS, IIMT COLLEGE OF PHARMACY, GREATER NOIDA
4. DR. K N MODI UNIVERSITY, NEWAI , RAJASTHAN

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR DETAILS:

Kamal Singh Bani

AFFILIATION- IIMT COLLEGE OF PHARMACY , GREATER NOIDA, G.B.NAGAR,
U.P & DR. K N MODI UNIVERSITY, NEWAI , RAJASTHAN

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ABSTRACT

The primary goal of postmarketing surveillance is to provide information for risk assessment of a drug. Drugs affecting the central nervous system form a unique group of products for surveillance because they are often misused, abused, and diverted. These medications include opioid analgesics, stimulants, sedative-hypnotics, muscle relaxants, anticonvulsants and other drug classes. Their adverse events are difficult to monitor because the perpetrator often attempts to conceal the misuse, abuse and diversion of the product. The Food and Drug Administration Amendments Act of 2007 includes generic opioid analgesic products by requiring that all products containing potent opioid drugs perform rigorous surveillance and risk management. While general risk management guidance has been developed by FDA, more specific analyses and guidance are needed to improve surveillance methodology for drugs which are misused, abused, diverted. Postmarketing drug surveillance refers to the monitoring of drugs once they reach the market after clinical trials. It evaluates drugs taken by individuals under a wide range of circumstances over an extended period of time. Such surveillance is much more likely to detect previously unrecognized positive or negative effects that may be associated with a drug. The majority of postmarketing surveillance concern adverse drug reactions (ADRs) monitoring and evaluation. Other important postmarketing surveillance components include unapproved or off-label drug use, problems with orphan drugs, and lack of paediatric formulations, as well as issues concerning international clinical trials in paediatric population. The process of evaluating and improving the safety of medicines used in paediatric practice is referred to as paediatric pharmacovigilance. It requires special attention. Childhood diseases and disorders may be qualitatively and quantitatively different from their adult equivalents. This may affect either benefit or risk of therapies (or both), with a resulting impact on the risk/benefit balance. In addition, chronic conditions may require chronic treatment and susceptibility to ADRs may change throughout the patient's lifetime according to age and stage of growth and development. Therefore, paediatric pharmacovigilance aspects need to be tailored to a number of variables based on heterogeneity of paediatric population. This article will summarize and discuss the key issues.

KEYWORDS :- Adverse drug reation, Surveillance,Clinical trails,Pharmacovigilance, Heterogeneity

INTRODUCTION

All medicines have benefits and risks. In traditional pharmacoepidemiology, the goal of signal detection is to identify unexpected risks occurring when a drug is used for medical care that were not evident during clinical trials. The majority of exposures to any approved prescription medication occur among patients prescribed the drug, and benefit/risk assessments in clinical trials are designed primarily to detect adverse events in the targeted patient population.

Medications that are subject to restrictions under the 1961 Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs and the 1971 Convention on Psychotropic Substances also have benefits and risks that affect non-patients (i.e., those not directly prescribed the drug); in the United States provisions in these international treaties are enacted through the Controlled Substances Act of 1970 and subsequent regulations. The debate over the right balance between benefit and risk of psychoactive substances has been a concern of the medical profession for hundreds of years[1]. In the twentieth century notable debates over the medical use of morphine, heroin, cannabis, amphetamine, methamphetamine, synthetic hallucinogens, and other drugs resulted in various legal and medical compromises. Beyond clinical trials, information from routine clinical experience is used to inform the broader societal debate, ranging from anecdotal observations by health care providers to formal systems of post-marketing surveillance.

Over the last two decades the United States has witnessed a rapid increase in the outpatient use of new formulations of controlled substances used to manage pain, attention deficit disorders, anxiety, insomnia and other disorders, a trend mirrored in western Europe, Australia, and elsewhere [2]. The major acute clinical adverse effects in patient populations that are associated with the most commonly prescribed controlled substances (e.g., opioids, psychostimulants, benzodiazepines) are well known; one of the greatest challenges in post-marketing surveillance remains measuring the risks in non-patients. In adults this includes abuse, addiction, diversion, overdose and consequences of injection, especially of those drug formulations not intended for parenteral use. Although it is generally assumed that use by non-patients is not related to any potential benefit, there may be tangible medical benefits such as self-medication for the treatment of pain or to stave off withdrawal symptom, separate from euphoria. Historically, post-marketing surveillance has relied on passive “spontaneous” reporting from health care providers and patients to the drug’s manufacturer, which is eventually submitted to the regulatory agency, or directly to the regulatory agency. Analysis of these pharmacovigilance data for most medications has traditionally been the domain of the national regulatory agencies, pharmaceutical companies and academics. With the increasing availability of electronic data on medical service utilization, new tools for quantifying benefits and risks of controlled substances have become available to a broader community of health scientists and policy makers. Yet there is limited formal guidance on determining when or where a problem exists in the context of controlled substances beyond scheduling and drug approval mechanisms.

Central to the current discussion about societal benefits and risks of controlled substances is knowing how to identify the emergence of a problem that requires attention or action, broadly defined as a “signal.” Historically, defining a signal for controlled substances has been difficult because no specific empirical criteria have been established through regulatory actions or guidances. There are no a priori levels of acceptable amounts of abuse, dependence, diversion, overdose, and injection that may occur with a drug that correspond to its regulation. While society, politicians and regulators may expect that no cases of these adverse events will occur, the long human experience with controlled substances shows that this is not feasible. The delicate question of what constitutes a signal is a dynamic challenge, one that is informed by local circumstances and beliefs, and is likely to change over time.

The responsibility for the safe use of a new medication begins with the manufacturer of the drug, and is formalized through risk management plans, now called risk evaluation and mitigation strategies (REMS) in the United States[3]. These plans are authored by the innovator company applying for permission to sell a new drug, in consultation with regulatory agencies; the responsibilities of generic manufacturers regarding REMS have not been well defined. The goals of many pharmaceutical industry risk management plans for controlled substances include measuring and minimizing overdose, both accidental and intentional, abuse, dependence, diversion, injection/tampering with the dosage form and accidental pediatric exposures. To fulfill the obligations set forth in these plans, surveillance for controlled substances must monitor well-characterized sets of patients and non-patients among whom these events are most likely to occur. Data sources may include law enforcement agencies, patients entering drug abuse treatment programs, poison centers, hospital emergency departments, key informants, the news media, the Internet, and studies conducted by government or academic groups. These data can be qualitative or quantitative, making it inherently difficult to “calculate” what would constitute a signal.

In this paper we focus on signal detection in the post-marketing setting, that is, after the drug has been approved and is available for general medical use. Post-marketing surveillance programs should be informed by pre-market risk assessment that addresses issues raised in preclinical and clinical studies, specifically utilizing studies of abuse potential of the active compound and the formulation, and the prospective collection of data on and assessment of protocol violations that occurred during clinical trials [4].

We also hope to provide some insight into the complex process of signal determination, from both quantitative and qualitative perspectives, drawing on examples from opioids where the most work has been conducted to date. We define signal determination to encompass the entire process starting with the collection of surveillance data, statistical or qualitative identification of potential signals, information gathering for further investigation, integrated signal assessment, and linking of a signal to an intervention.

Reports from the National Survey of Drug Use and Health (NSDUH) and other sources indicate that the majority of those who endorse non-medical use of specific prescription drugs also are involved in the non-medical use of multiple prescription and illicit drugs [5-8]. Therefore, if a signal is generated regarding the abuse of a specific branded or generic drug, the most stringent intervention regarding the availability of the drug (i.e., withdrawal from the market) will do little to reduce the problem of prescription drug abuse, and will most likely have negative consequences for the patients who most need the medication. Since polysubstance use can cause problems that are not limited to a specific drug, it is unreasonable to accept that a single pharmaceutical company will be able to make a significant impact on the broader problem. Greater restriction on distribution through drug scheduling is only one tool available to federal agencies to prevent unintended consequences of drug availability. Similarly, restricted pharmaceutical marketing practices may have limited potential to avert dangerous use of a controlled substance; for example, the increased use of methadone for pain management during the 2000s in the United States has paralleled an exponential increase in mortality from the drug[9], despite no marketing efforts by the manufacturers. As data sources for post-marketing surveillance have expanded, so have the potential stakeholders who can set policies or issue recommendations that affect the availability of controlled substances. These stakeholders include health insurance companies, government-sponsored pharmacy benefit programs, state and local health authorities, professional associations, pharmaceutical companies, patient advocacy groups, family members and patients who have suffered adverse effects, and medical licensing boards, all of whom have had an increasingly larger role in translating observed signals to interventions.

Therefore, the audience of this paper is intended to include parties, beyond the pharmaceutical industry and government regulatory agencies, which may also be involved in public health decision making regarding the benefits and risks of a pharmaceutical controlled substance.

Broadly defined, a signal can arise from events that occur in an unexpected manner, whether by their frequency, location or nature. The International Conference on Harmonisation (ICH) guidance on pharmacovigilance planning (E2E) defines a signal for an adverse event without the need for causal connection: “any unfavorable and unintended sign (including an abnormal laboratory finding, for example), symptom, or disease temporally associated with the use of a medicinal product, whether or not considered related to the medicinal product” [10-11] presents a supporting definition that emphasizes the process of gathering information: “a set of data constituting a hypothesis that is relevant to the rational and safe use of a medicine. Such data are usually clinical, pharmacological, pathological or epidemiological in nature. A signal consists of a hypothesis together with data and arguments.” As computing power and methodological sophistication advance, the development of statistical algorithms has led to an emphasis of “signals” as output from mathematical processes. However, our experience suggests that applied signal detection remains highly dependent on human intelligence and clinical judgment, albeit with the assistance of statistical tools.

Out of practicality, signal definitions are often linked to the types of events that drive companies, health authorities, regulators, or individuals to action (interventions). As in other areas of public health, effective surveillance systems for controlled substance-related adverse events should be structured enough to identify known action triggers, but also flexible enough to detect new unexpected events. The majority of opioid analgesics and psychostimulants approved in the last two decades have been reformulations of existing therapies that contain reference listed drugs (i.e., active pharmaceutical ingredients with known properties); this differentiates post-marketing surveillance for these drugs and other controlled substances from new molecular entities for which the adverse event profile is less well understood. However, our knowledge of uncommon adverse events associated with controlled substances is not as complete as we might think and additional consequences are coming to light over time. For example, pulmonary complications from injecting talc-containing formulations have been observed for prescription opioids [12] and stimulants[13], and have been included in labeled warnings for some talc-containing opioids [14], but have been considerably less studied and are not at this time addressed in risk management plans.

Signals can result from analyses of national-level aggregate data, community-level data and from case reports. Each level of aggregation results in signals of a different nature and encompasses different domains of concern, underscoring the difficulty in defining what constitutes a signal ahead of time. Both qualitative and quantitative information may give rise to signals. In any of these cases, evaluation of a potential signal is critical to assess the veracity of the signal and determine if there is any remedy (intervention) that can be enacted, commensurate with the nature and intensity of the signal.

Consistent with public health surveillance systems for other diseases, surveillance for controlled substances involves a tripartite progression from reports to potential signals to verified signals, in both patient and non-patient populations; verified signals would then trigger actions. This process is similar to current pharmacovigilance practices, where a case report called into a company is followed-up to collect more information, and may eventually be confirmed as an actual event of concern with corresponding reporting requirements.

At the time of licensing by regulatory bodies, such as the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency, not all adverse events or risks associated with a medication may have been identified. Therefore, postmarketing surveillance is essential for providing data on drug safety through monitoring the use of a medication, the types of patients receiving treatment, the outcomes of treatment, and the occurrence of adverse drug reactions (ADRs). The “science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse events or any other drug-related problem” has been termed “pharmacovigilance” [15]

In September 2008, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) introduced specific pharmacovigilance guidelines that supersede many of the provisions contained in the United Kingdom’s Medication Act (1968). These guidelines highlight the importance of traditional postmarketing surveillance methods, such as the Yellow Card scheme and encourage the introduction of systematically collected data using registries. Although disease or drug exposure registries may have an important function in postmarketing surveillance, their precise role in pharmacovigilance remains unclear.

Postmarketing drug surveillance has historically relied on data from clinical trials or epidemiological studies. Postmarketing randomized controlled trials (RCTs), such as the Adenomatous Polyp Prevention on Vioxx (APPROVe) trial that prompted the global withdrawal of Vioxx (rofecoxib) [16], are expensive and are not routinely powered to detect rare ADRs, those with a long latency or events occurring in specific (and often excluded) patient groups [17]. As such, epidemiological methods, such as spontaneous reporting systems (SRS), have long been recognized as useful tools in drug-safety monitoring. The Yellow Card scheme adopted in the United Kingdom more than 40 years ago has become an important detection system for prescribers, and now patients, to voluntarily report ADRs. Spontaneous reporting has proven useful for capturing ADRs occurring in the initial period after treatment; however, this method does not define the population from which reports arise (the “denominator”), leading to poor estimation of the incidence of ADRs especially in long-term drug use. Despite previous success of SRS schemes in identifying rare ADRs, some have questioned the future legitimacy of this method, citing its low position in the hierarchy of evidence and persisting problems of underreporting [18].

A clinical registry is a register of patients in a particular clinical setting, recording treatment and outcomes of all patients within the institution/units involved and collecting information on variables that facilitates risk adjustment. Registries have become increasingly appealing in postmarketing surveillance of medications; however, their exact role continues to evolve. Registries are of most value for providing drug safety data through monitoring the incidence of rare adverse events particularly for high cost and/or highly specialized drugs. In the United Kingdom and Europe, for licensing new medications, pediatric administrations, or when changes are made to a drug’s manufacturing process, the new EMA guidelines now require detailed risk management plans, in which clinical registries may find greater inclusion as tools to detect ADRs.

The changes made to the EMA guidelines provide a mechanism for the detection of rare adverse events after even subtle modifications in the manufacturing of medications or biological agents. A manufacturing change that replaced human serum albumin with polysorbate 80 and glycine in the formulation of Eprex (epoetin alpha—a medication licensed for use in patients with chronic renal failure) was reported to be associated with an increased incidence of pure red cell aplasia (PRCA): an extremely rare adverse outcome undetected by premarketing studies [19]. Whereas findings from spontaneous reports were used to estimate the incidence of PRCA in patients receiving Eprex, the need to prospectively study the rate of PRCA in chronic renal failure patients treated with erythropoiesis-stimulating agents, such as Eprex, has resulted in the establishment of the Prospective Immunogenicity Surveillance (PRIMS) registry [20]. Under the new EMA guidelines, registries, such as PRIMS may be useful ADR detection tools in situations where RCTs have not identified rare or latent ADRs, such as PRCA in this population. As such, the PRIMS registry provides a novel method for recruiting and following a large cohort of patients (a total of 20,000 person years exposure to Eprex) receiving erythropoiesis-stimulating agents to continually monitor the safety of this agent in real world populations.

In postmarketing surveillance settings, registries offer a number of advantages over other approaches for investigating the safety of therapeutics. In contrast to the tightly controlled patient selection approach adopted by clinical trials, registries provide a more representative picture of the range of patients receiving a drug, their additional medications, and existing medical condition. For monitoring the safety of medications used in the treatment of Rheumatoid arthritis (RA), a number of registries have been established that aim to provide data across the full range of medicated patients. Two such registries—the British Society for Rheumatology Biologics Register (BSRBR) and the Australian Rheumatology Association Database (ARAD)—were established to monitor the use and safety of therapeutics in RA patients. Launched in 2001, the BSRBR has provided important data on the long-term safety of antitumor necrosis factor therapies and their relationships with serious infections, myocardial infarction, and congenital malformations in pregnant patients. The ARAD was established to obtain more representative data on the use of biological disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) in Australia and provide better estimates of the incidence of ADRs in RA patients treated with DMARDs. This national registry has become a useful tool for monitoring quality of life, health care utilization, and the impact of therapy switching in a clinically representative cohort of patients, of whom just 5% meet the inclusion criteria of published RCTs [21].

In acute care pharmacovigilance, registries have been developed to monitor the safety of highly specialized medications. The Haemostasis Registry was initiated to study the use of Recombinant Activated Factor VII (rFVIIa, Novo Nordisk Pharmaceuticals Pty. Ltd.) in off-licence settings in Australia and New Zealand, with a focus on detecting the incidence of thromboembolic adverse events (TAEs). This medication, approved for use in patients with Hemophilia A and B with inhibitors, has gained widespread use in other settings of critical bleeding, such as trauma and cardiac and liver surgery. As the Haemostasis Registry includes all patients receiving off-licence rFVIIa at participating hospitals, reliable estimates of the incidence of TAEs across this defined population can be made. Recently, a study from the Registry assessed the adverse outcomes of Registry cardiac surgery patients in comparison with cardiac surgery patients included in the Australasian Society for Cardiothoracic Surgery (ASCTS) Cardiac Surgery Database and found no statistically significant difference in the rate of TAEs [22].

As a component of pharmacovigilance systems, clinical registries offer a means of providing credible, reliable, and epidemiologically sound data elements. The collection of a core set of data items is done through a standardized process, allowing reliable comparison of patients and outcomes treated at different centers and over time. These standardized data are critical for ensuring registry reliability, however, a narrow scope of data collection may result in missed ADRs attributable to unanticipated drug reactions. Although a registry cannot collect all information relating to a patient's treatment, the reliable and standardized collection of predefined data items allows registries to provide a sufficient level of risk adjustment. Registries' methods are therefore distinct from other databases' methods that have been used for pharmacovigilance, such as data-linkage techniques between population level administrative database (including health insurance databases) and prescribing records used to examine the use of medications in pregnancy. Improvements in data-linkage techniques through the development of unique identifiers, coupled with greater access to routine data, have the capacity to add a cost-effective surveillance method to future pharmacovigilance initiatives.[23]

Interest in registries as postmarketing surveillance tools for specialized or high-cost pharmaceuticals continues to gain attention from manufacturers, academics, regulatory authorities, and subsidizing schemes, such as the Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) in Australia. The introduction of the Bosentan Patient Registry (BPR) demonstrates an innovative risk-sharing arrangement between a manufacturer and the government. In 2004, Bosentan was listed by the PBS for the treatment of patients with idiopathic pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH): a disease considered to carry a poor prognosis. The subsidy provided by the PBS for Bosentan was based on the improvements in life expectancy resulting from treatment; however, long-term clinical trials had failed to confirm this finding. As a result, the BPR was established to collect outcome data from all patients receiving Bosentan in Australia to assess the accuracy of internationally conducted clinical trials. In this setting, licensing of Bosentan for the treatment of PAH in Australia was dependent on the establishment and maintenance of the BPR.[24]

The experiences of PRIMS, Haemostasis Registry, BSRBR, ARAD, and BPR highlight the use and potential role of large scale, prospectively collected, epidemiologically sound data sources in pharmacovigilance systems. However, registries are not without limitations. A number of pregnancy registries have been established, such as the Lamotrigine (LTG) Pregnancy Registry, to investigate the use of anticonvulsant medications in pregnant women because of the potential for drug exposure early in pregnancy, the possible link with congenital malformations, and the risk of teratogenicity associated with polytherapy. Data from the registry appear to indicate that the risks associated with LTG are similar to those in the general population; however, more definitive conclusions will only be possible with greater case numbers [25]. Criticisms have been made that such data collections are prone to selection bias when based on volunteering women, resulting in exclusion of the most at-risk patient groups and therefore serious underestimation of ADR rates. Therefore, minimizing patient dropout (particularly of certain subgroups, such as those with greater illness severity) and ensuring data completeness are critical for enabling registries to detect ADRs with long latency periods. "Opt-off" consent procedures, whereby patient data are included on the registry unless a patient lodges an objection, have been recommended as one method for ensuring complete case ascertainment and minimizing selection bias [26].

Collection of additional variables beyond core parameters adds considerable costs to the financial inputs required to maintain standardized data collection, training of data collectors, access to medical records, complete case ascertainment, and database expenses associated with registries. For the Haemostasis Registry, the BSRBR, and the BPR, funding for all operations has been provided by the drug manufacturers whereas the management of the registries and the publication of results are the responsibility of independent academic institutions. Similar to other registries, such as the Consortium of Rheumatology Researchers of North America, the independence of these registries from industry influence is essential in providing objective and unbiased research findings. In Europe, this distinction is even clearer, with pharmaceutical companies mandated to support postmarketing independent data collections. Because of the significant costs associated with registries and the common need for external support, registries are of most value for the postmarketing surveillance of expensive or highly specialized medications in highly significant clinical contexts. Unlike RCTs or case-control studies, drug registries are often limited to analyses of specific agents or medications, such as rFVIIa or Bosentan. As a result, registries do not routinely include control groups of similar patients not receiving the medication and are therefore not able to address questions of relative efficacy or treatment effect. Registries, such as the ARAD and the BSRBR have taken steps to recruit control samples

of patients whereas other registries have initiated data-linkage efforts with other existing sources, such as the Haemostasis Registry's link with ASCTS. Health insurance databases offer another useful resource for reliably capturing large numbers of patients, monitoring the course of disease, assessing drug utilization, and following patient groups over long time horizons. Because of a lack of clinical detail in these databases, linkage to clinical registries is becoming increasingly useful, facilitating a linked-data source which minimizes selection bias, allows identification of a control group, and contains detailed clinical data for sufficient risk adjustment.[27]

The questions that may be investigated using registry data are therefore often restricted to those concerned with rates and patterns of potentially linked ADRs and events that may not occur immediately after drug administration. Therefore, registries are not designed to provide conclusive evidence of treatment efficacy or effectiveness and cannot serve as replacements for clinical trials. As tools for monitoring the safety and usage of pharmaceuticals and other therapeutic agents, registries are superior to all other postmarketing surveillance methods for identifying patterns of use and outcomes as well as applications that may benefit from further exploration and possible clinical trials.[28]

All drugs are capable of producing adverse effects and whenever a drug is given a risk is taken. The magnitude of risk has to be considered along with the magnitude of expected therapeutic benefit in deciding whether to use or not to use a particular drug in a given patient [29]. Lazarou et al., 1998 has suggested that adverse drug reactions are the fourth to the sixth commonest cause of death [30]. About 6.5% to 6.89% of all hospital admissions are due to (ADRs) which increase the duration of hospital stay and the cost incurred upon the patient [31,32]. Patelet et al., 2007 reported that more than 50% of ADRs are definitely or potentially avoidable [33].

During the drug development process (Phase 1-Phase 3), adverse drug reactions are reported to the regulatory authorities and ethical committees in the form of drug safety update reports (DSURs). If any adverse drug reaction occurs during the trial, the principal investigator reports to the sponsor within 24hrs and to the Institutional review board (IRB) within 14 working days. Further, the sponsor reports to the regulatory authorities within 14 calendar days. Due to homogenous population sample (strict inclusion/exclusion criteria, subjects having single disease, specific groups of children, elderly and pregnant women being excluded), small sample size (detection of rare adverse effect is difficult), shorter duration of a trial (limits the detection of long term adverse effects), inability to detect ADRs under real life situations (drug interaction, drug food interactions etc.). Thus, there is an urgent need for a system which keeps an eye on the ADRs of the medicinal products [34].

Pharmacovigilance is mainly the phase 4 of drug development process and also known as post marketing surveillance. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines Pharmacovigilance as a science related to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse reactions towards a medicinal product or any other medicine related problems in human beings [35]. The main objective of pharmacovigilance is to quantify previously recognized adverse drug reactions, to identify unrecognized adverse drug events, to evaluate the effectiveness of medicines in real-world situations, and to decrease mortality and morbidity associated with adverse events [36,37].

Signal detection and its assessment is the most important aspect of pharmacovigilance [38]. The WHO defines a signal as: 'Reported information on a possible causal relationship between an adverse event and a drug, of which the relationship is unknown or incompletely documented previously'. Often, a limited number of reports represent a signal [39]. These signals are reported to regional pharmacovigilance centres followed by zonal centres. Finally, all case reports are filed in databases at the National Centres as well as sent onto the WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring (the Uppsala Monitoring Centre) [40]. Further, signal assessment is performed using Uppsala Monitoring scale (UMC) & Naranjo scale of probability to analyse the cause and effect analysis. Signal detection and its assessment is very vital and complex process. Thus, in this review, we have tried to compile the qualitative methods of signal detection and its assessment used in pharmacovigilance.

The early detection of safety signals as soon as possible is increasingly important and of great interest to the pharmaceutical industry, regulators, and the public domain. Signals have both qualitative and quantitative aspects. Different categories of adverse events need different methodologies for detection. The primary function of pharmacovigilance is early detection of signals [41]. In 1960s, thalidomide tragedy occurred due to late signal detection [42]. However, spontaneous reporting systems have now been developed and used all around the world. The number of case reports received by the World Health Organization (WHOUMC) collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring in Uppsala, Sweden is continuously rising and now numbers almost 2,00,000 per year [43]

Conclusion

Assessment of misuse, abuse, and diversion of prescription drugs must address its occult nature and involves fundamentally different surveillance compared to other pharmaceutical products. Current best practice is to use multiple detection systems to assess misuse, abuse and diversion of CNS active drugs by various populations in a timely, sensitive, and specific manner. To make matters more complex, some controlled substances are prescribed for the treatment of addiction, and therefore, are being prescribed and taken by the population most at risk for non-medical use of the drug, referred to as confounding by indication in pharmacoepidemiology. Underreporting of adverse events is one of the significant global setbacks. Although the drug has been introduced into the market only after its safety and efficacy have been approved, it is important to recognize that the risks involved with the drugs come to light only when the drug is introduced into the market. This is because clinical trials used to prove the safety and efficacy involve strict inclusion and exclusion criteria which restrict the study of drugs in special age groups like children, elderly as well as pregnant women that are usually not analyzed during the clinical trials; factors that result in reactions caused by a drug like the drug-drug interactions, generic as well as environmental factors. This demands the need for Post-marketing Pharmacovigilance. This report demonstrates how post-marketing surveillance can be used to identify and evaluate those rare adverse experiences that might not be observed during the clinical trials and also shows the importance of making every effort in highlighting the field of pharmacovigilance to improve the safety and improve their quality of life of patients.

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